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TEACHER TRAINING IN MATHEMATICS: A LOOK AT THE CURRICULUM APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, education faces numerous challenges and transformations driven by technological advances, globalization and changes in social and economic demands. Given this dynamic scenario, ongoing teacher training is essential to ensure the quality of teaching and adaptation to new educational realities. This paper presents the final results of the research carried out in the Master's Degree in Educational Sciences, which analyzed the Continuing Education of teachers and its articulation with pedagogical practice; the Elementary School curriculum, in the area of mathematics, in the final years; mathematics teacher training and its contribution to pedagogical practice; the Pernambuco Curriculum and aspects related to mathematics education; the teaching protagonism and its interaction with the Curriculum. Researchers in this theoretical field, such as Tardif (2012), Moran (2019) and Morin (2011), argue that we must pay close attention to the continuing education offered to these subjects.

KEYWORDS: Teacher Training. Pedagogical Practice. Mathematics Curriculum